

Original Research

Genetic Differentiation of *Clarias gariepinus* From Nigerian's Rivers Benue and Donga Using Single Nucleotide Polymorphism

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ABSTRACT

Clarias gariepinus (Burchell, 1822), a cornerstone of aquaculture in Nigeria, faces threats to its genetic integrity due to indiscriminate breeding and environmental degradation. This study investigates the genetic differentiation of *C. gariepinus* broodstocks from Rivers Benue and Donga using single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) markers derived from the mitochondrial 16S rRNA gene. A total of 30 specimens were collected, with 29 successfully sequenced and analyzed. DNA was extracted, and amplification was performed using species-specific primers. BioEdit and MEGA X were used for sequence alignment, SNP identification, and phylogenetic analysis. Results revealed high sequence similarity (99.0–100%) with the *C. gariepinus* reference genome (NCBI: KT001082.1), confirming species identity. Low sequence divergence was observed, reflecting high genetic homogeneity within this population. Nucleotide composition was slightly A–T rich, and the transition/transversion bias was $R = 2768.32$. Only one SNP (T/C at locus 431) differentiated the three haplotypes identified, while the Tajima's relative rate test showed no significant differences in evolutionary rates among haplotypes ($\chi^2 = 0.00$; $p = 1.000$). In conclusion, the low haplotypic diversity and absence of functional mutations reflect genetic homogeneity among the populations studied. However, complementary analyses using DNA markers are required to fully understand the genetic differentiation in *C. gariepinus*.

Keywords: *Clarias gariepinus*, single nucleotide polymorphism, mitochondrial RNA, genetic diversity, Rivers Benue and Donga

INTRODUCTION

Clarias gariepinus (Burchell, 1822), commonly known as the African sharptooth catfish, is one of the most economically significant aquaculture species in Africa due to its rapid growth rate, high feed conversion efficiency, and adaptability to diverse environmental conditions (Olaniyi et al., 2018; Adewolu and Adeniji, 2020). In Nigeria, *C. gariepinus* forms the backbone of the aquaculture industry, contributing significantly to national fish production, food security, and income generation (Adewumi and Olaleye, 2011; FAO, 2022). However, the genetic integrity of farmed

and natural populations is increasingly under threat due to indiscriminate breeding practices, habitat degradation, and the introduction of non-native strains (Imron et al., 2019; Oboh and Adebayo, 2021).

In Nigeria, the African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) is predominantly cultured using intensive systems such as earthen ponds, tanks, and cages, which offer enhanced control over feeding, water quality, and disease management (FAO, 2020). This approach maximizes productivity but also presents challenges. Common issues include disease outbreaks, poor-quality or insufficient feed, substandard hatchery practices, and

environmental problems like water pollution and oxygen depletion (Ajani et al., 2016; Obasa et al., 2020). These constraints limit optimal performance and sustainability. Addressing these problems through improved management practices, quality inputs, and regulatory support is critical to strengthening the viability and expansion of *C. gariepinus* aquaculture in Nigeria.

Genetic characterization is critical for effective broodstock management and sustainable aquaculture production. Among the various molecular markers available, Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNPs) have emerged as powerful tools for assessing genetic variation, population structure, and evolutionary relationships due to their abundance, stability, and high resolution (Vignal et al., 2002; Seeb et al., 2011). SNP markers provide valuable insights into the differentiation of closely related populations, enabling the identification of distinct genetic stocks necessary for effective breeding programs (Yarez et al., 2015).

The Rivers Benue and Donga are two major tributaries of the River Niger system, supporting important natural populations of *C. gariepinus*. Despite their ecological and economic significance, little is known about the genetic differentiation between *C. gariepinus* broodstocks from these rivers. Understanding the genetic diversity of these populations is essential to avoid inbreeding depression, maintain adaptive potential, and enhance broodstock performance in aquaculture systems (Muchlisin et al., 2020; Mekkawy et al., 2022). This study aims to assess the genetic differentiation of *C. gariepinus* broodstock from Rivers Benue and Donga using SNP markers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Description of the Sampling Rivers

The samples were collected from River Benue and Donga. River Benue lies between latitude 8°10'58.3"N and longitude 9°44'42.32"E, while Donga River lies between latitude 7°43'00"N and longitude 10°03'00"E. It has an area of 3,121 km². The rivers exist year-round; the water volume fluctuates with seasons. The rivers overflow their banks during the rainy season (May-October) but decrease drastically in volume, leaving

tiny islands in the middle of the river during the dry season (November-April) (Figure 1). The river contains several species of fish that are of economic importance to the people of Taraba State and Nigeria at large (Inger et al., 2005).

Figure 1: Locations of river Benue and its Tributary river Donga

Sample Collection

A total of 30 *C. gariepinus* broodstocks (average weight: 1000–1500 g), comprising both sexes, were purchased from artisanal fishers in the Benue and Donga Rivers between January and June 2020. External examination for morphological abnormalities was conducted at the landing sites. Specimens were transported in plastic troughs (60 cm diameter × 30 cm depth) to Kahzuh Integrated Farm Limited, Ibi LGA, Taraba State.

Acclimation and Genotypic Sampling

Broodstocks were acclimated for eight weeks in movable fish holding units. During this period, 1 g caudal fin clips was collected from each specimen and sent to the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Ibadan, for DNA extraction and genotyping using the 16S rRNA gene marker, following standard molecular protocols (Stephen *et al.*, 1983; Kumar *et al.*, 2018).

DNA Extraction and PCR Amplification

DNA was extracted using the Dellaporta method (Stephen *et al.*, 1983). Fin tissues were macerated and processed with SDS and potassium acetate. Precipitated DNA was washed with ethanol, dried, and resuspended in TE buffer, then stored at -20°C . PCR was performed with primers 16Sar-F and 16Sbr-R targeting the 16S rRNA gene (Felsenstein, 1985; Tamura *et al.*, 2004). Each reaction used GoTaq reagents and G2 DNA polymerase, and amplification was conducted using a GeneAmp 9700 Bio-Rad T100TM thermal cycler with optimized cycling parameters of denaturation at 94°C for 30 seconds and final extension at 72°C for 7 minutes

Gel Electrophoresis, PCR Integrity, Purification and Sequencing

Amplicons (~1.5 kb) were validated via 1.5% agarose gel electrophoresis stained with ethidium bromide and visualized under UV light, using a GeneRulerTM 100 bp DNA ladder for fragment sizing. PCR products were ethanol-purified using sodium acetate and ethanol precipitation. Purified amplicons were sequenced with the ABI 3130xl Genetic Analyzer using BigDye Terminator v3.1 chemistry.

Genetic Diversity and Evolutionary Analysis

Sequence quality was verified and aligned in BioEdit. MEGA X was used for downstream analyses, including nucleotide diversity and substitution pattern estimation using Kimura's two-parameter model (Kimura, 1980; Kumar *et al.*, 2018).

SNP Identification and Functional Annotation

Unique SNPs distinguishing haplotypes were identified using alignment-based methods and assessed for statistical significance using Tajima's relative rate test

(Tajima, 1993). Functional implications of SNPs were inferred through codon translation analysis in MEGA X.

Data Analysis

BioEdit and MEGA X were employed for sequence alignment and phylogenetic analysis. BioEdit was used for manual editing and integration with ClustalW and BLAST.

RESULTS

Genetic Diversity of *Clarias gariepinus* Haplotypes

The specimens amplified successfully during PCR (Figure 2) matched the *C. gariepinus* mitochondrial genome (NCBI Accession: KT001082.1), with coverage of 99.8%. Sequence identity scores ranged between 99.0% and 100%. Nineteen specimens (65.5%) had 99.0% genome coverage, while ten (34.5%) had 100%.

Figure 2: Gel Electropherogram showing amplification of the PCR of *C. gariepinus* specimens

*Lane: L indicates ladder

Nucleotide Composition and Substitution Pattern

The Maximum Composite Likelihood Estimate showed nucleotide composition as follows: A=30.46%, T/U=21.94%, C=24.25%, and G=23.35%. Transition/transversion bias (R) was estimated at 2768.32 under equal nucleotide frequencies (Table 1). The maximum log-likelihood score for tree topology estimation was -800.987.

Table 1: Estimation of the Pattern of Nucleotide Substitution

Nucleotides	A	T	C	G
A	-	0.41	0.45	0
T	0.56	-	50.56	0.43
C	0.56	45.73	-	0.43
G	0	0.41	0.45	-

Legend: A: Adenine, T: Thymine, C: Cytosine, G: Guanine

Haplotype Differentiation and Evolutionary Rates

Tajima’s relative rate test (Table 2) showed one unique nucleotide difference at locus 431 (T/C SNP), separating haplotype 1 from the others (Figure 3). Chi-square analysis ($\chi^2 = 0.00$, $p = 1.000$) indicated equal evolutionary rates between haplotypes.

Table 2: Tajima's Relative Rate Test for Nucleotide Sequences of the Three Haplotypes

Configuration	Count
Identical sites in all three sequences	557
Divergent sites in all three sequences	0
Unique differences in haplotype 3	0
Unique differences in haplotype 2	0
Unique differences in haplotype 1	1

Functional Analysis of SNPs

A single nucleotide polymorphism (C to T) was observed at locus 431, with haplotype 1 retaining C and others showing T (figure 3). Translation analysis showed that this SNP was synonymous, with no observable change in amino acid sequence (Figure 4).

DISCUSSION

The high sequence identity (99.0–100%) and coverage confirm the mitochondrial identity of the specimens as *Clarias gariepinus*, consistent with NCBI reference KT001082.1. This supports effective species identification using mitochondrial markers. Similar results were reported by [Anene et al. \(2020\)](#), who achieved over 98% identity in *C. gariepinus* sequences from Nigerian rivers, emphasizing the reliability of mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) for species validation.

Figure 3: Nucleotides alignment showing C/T SNP position at Locus 431

The low sequence divergence suggests high genetic similarity within this population, reflecting findings by [Okomoda et al. \(2019\)](#), who noted genetic homogeneity in farmed and wild *Clarias* stocks in Nigeria. Such genetic homogeneity may indicate limited historical separation or gene flow among populations in the Benue and Donga rivers.

The nucleotide composition was slightly A-T rich, which aligns with mitochondrial genomic patterns observed in vertebrates ([Saccone et al., 1999](#)). The transition/transversion bias ($R = 2768.32$) was significantly high, in agreement with previous studies by [Brown et al. \(1982\)](#) and [Mwangi et al. \(2017\)](#), who reported higher transition rates due to their lower mutational impact and stability in coding regions. This

high transition frequency supports the notion that mitochondrial DNA evolves under selective constraints, particularly in conserved protein-coding regions, where non-synonymous mutations are often deleterious.

Figure 4: Amino acid sequence of *C. gariepinus* from rivers Benue and Donga, Nigeria

*Mutation site arrowed

Only one SNP (T/C at locus 431) differentiated the three haplotypes identified. This suggests low haplotypic diversity, which corroborates the findings of [Okeyoyin and Moodley \(2021\)](#), who observed

minimal haplotype variation in *C. gariepinus* populations from Nigerian inland waters. This limited variation implies a narrow genetic base, which may constrain the adaptability and selective breeding potential of these broodstock in aquaculture. Tajima's test revealed no significant difference in evolutionary rates among haplotypes ($p = 1.000$), suggesting similar mutational pressures and evolutionary trajectories. This may indicate recent divergence or sustained gene flow between river populations, a hypothesis also supported by [Ndiaye et al. \(2015\)](#) in their study on *Clarias anguillaris*.

Furthermore, the single SNP (T–C) observed at locus 431 with haplotype 1 retaining C and others showing T, translation analysis showed that this SNP was synonymous with no observable change in amino acid sequence, meaning it did not alter the encoded amino acid. Synonymous mutations are often considered selectively neutral and are frequently reported in mitochondrial genes ([Chamary et al., 2006](#)). While some studies suggest that such mutations can influence mRNA stability, splicing, or translational efficiency, these potential effects were not assessed in this study. [Okomoda et al. \(2020\)](#) similarly identified several synonymous SNPs in mitochondrial genes of *Clarias* species and emphasized their limited use in functional genomics but noted their utility in phylogenetic and evolutionary studies.

CONCLUSION

The low genetic variation among *Clarias gariepinus* haplotypes from the Benue and Donga rivers reveals a genetic homogeneity between these populations. Future studies might incorporate DNA markers and wider geographic sampling to capture more patterns of genetic differentiation.

ETHICS APPROVAL

All procedures performed in this study were in accordance with the institution's ethical standard.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares no conflict of interest.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTIONS

UNM set up the study and monitored it from beginning to end.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data set generated and analyzed during the current study is available from the corresponding author upon request.

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